

Sensibility in between: A phenomenology-inspired design proposition

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Abstract ‘Meaning’ is often considered to be held in a person (bodily and thinking capabilities) or in the qualities of artefacts (product characteristics). In contrast, within this paper, I propose to design for the emergence of meaning not only in the interaction but also in-between its participants. Anchored in the theories of the phenomenology of perception and ecological psychology this paper presents the Sensible Illumination concept, a lighting system for the home and work environment, functioning as a physical hypothesis to further both theoretical and design practical insights of the proposed interaction paradigm.

Keywords *Phenomenology-inspired design, Continuous Interaction, Engagement, Interaction design, Context-aware design*

Introduction

James Jerome Gibson (1986) has influenced interaction design over the past decades. Mostly with his work on *affordance*. Donald Norman popularized this concept through his book “The Psychology of Everyday Things” (Norman, 1988) which was later entitled “The Design of Everyday Things”. Norman uses the example of a door handle to elaborate that what we perceive is the opportunity to grasp (*affordance*) given by that our hands can grab (*effectivities*). Gibson emphasizes that the world is perceived as intrinsically meaningful as we are attuned to the world through our capabilities to perceive and act (Gibson, 1986). This emphasis on the lived body and its *effectivities* suggests that people perceive the world differently (i.e., for a child a chair is not sit-able but climbable).

While Gibson developed his ecological psychology, similar ideas emerged in philosophy. It was through Paul Dourish’s (2001) introduction of Maurice Merleau-Ponty’s “Phenomenology of Perception” (Merleau-Ponty, 1962) in “Where the Action Is: Foundations of Embodied Interaction” that the interaction design field got acquainted with this perspective that centralizes the experiencing body in the world.

According to Merleau-Ponty, people adjust themselves through skillful coping (Dreyfus, 2002) to what a situation requires. He speaks of the body’s quest for a *maximum grip*, a match of how the body can optimally deal with its environment. To him, meaning emerges *in* interaction with an attuning body while engaging with the world highlighting their (body and world) intertwining character. It is by acknowledging a subjective embodied character of our engagement with the ever-changing world that *contextuality* is of dynamic, intertwined and holistic nature (Dourish, 2004). Moreover, both ecological psychology and phenomenology stress the unity (reciprocity) between human beings and their environment, placing the interacting body central in existence and as primary means of experiencing the world (primacy of action).

Figure 1. The Sensible Illumination consisting of a series of light bulbs, and people. Both people and bulbs have action-perception loops to engage with the world. Where the directed intentionality meets, i.e., where a bulb wants to shed light and a person desires light, about-content light can be engaged with. Through engagement, meaning can emerge in-between.

Furthermore, Gibson’s resonance model, elaborated by Michaels and Carello (1981) in the form of a radio analogy, suggests that perception concerns the *tuning* of our body (as our perceptual system) to information, contrary to mentally capturing and storing information. We do so in holistic (*detection* not calculation) and continuous (in action no reflection) ways attuning to what is useful information. His theory of perceiving is a theory of knowing the environment. In other words, perceptions and actions themselves concern knowing, rather than having knowledge.

Design proposition

For design, this means that functionality reveals itself through interaction and builds upon the match between our human capabilities and those of the products at stake. The challenge is thus to design for human capabilities (Overbeeke, 2007) mapping its *continuous* qualities of being-in-the-world (*action-possibilities*) to the discrete power embodied in computing (*functionalities*) in a meaningful manner. Following that meaning emerges *in* the interaction between person and environment, *in-between* knowing systems; subsequently, we need to focus

designing on the *about-content* (i.e., dynamic match or meaning in between the body and the world) that brings about the meaning.

Design exploration

A lighting system for a home environment has been chosen as context for exploring the in-between-ness as inspiration for interaction design. The system concept, called Sensible Illumination, extends ordinary lighting with active and dynamic capabilities. Through framing the *action-possibilities* of the person and the *action-possibilities* incorporated in the behavior of the lighting: meaning is to emerge *in* the interaction and *in between* the lamps and persons. In other words, one continually engages with the light in context, not with the light bulb *per se*.

Interaction design and technical implementation

The interaction design of the Sensible Illumination is based on the idea to provide a person with light where it is needed or desired. The people carry a token that estimates this desire and signals this into the environment, which in its turn is receptive to this 'information.' This would be the lighting that thus perceives desires from people, which are as most lamps are capable of lighting up space. In terms of mapping people to the system, the *about-content* is light (which people desire and lamps can provide).

The underlying assumption that people desire light in front of them, in their field of gaze, was taken. And, that this desire is higher when the person is active contrary to inactive in which no light would be needed.

The lamps are *attuned* to *detect* the desire of people *continuously* while people direct their bodies to them. This desire is grounded in activity and whether the desire for light has been met already (i.e., environment light is involved in the interaction-loop).

Regarding the *about-content*, how the fields of people and lamps intersect: the *action-possibilities* of a person are in movement and directedness within and the *functionalities* of the lighting system are to merely intensify or dim light. It is designed for *about-content* to emerge at this intersection of person and environment/system: sensibly illuminating the active gaze of a person.

The Sensible Illumination prototype is built with Philips HUE lighting bulbs. Each bulb is sensible to the 'desire of light' in front of itself. Each person, in turn, is carrying a token that broadcasts the 'desire for light' in a forward direction. The higher the desire, the more light it demands. Within the prototype, the control of light is limited brightness and hue (warm – cold light). The Philips HUE lights that are usually discretely controlled are now updated at a rate of twenty times per second for a continuous interaction-loop to create light motion that feels direct and continuous, and thus to come forth to the continuous nature of perception.

Reflections

As part of the Concept-Driven Interaction Design Research approach (Stolterman & Wiberg, 2010) in which I aim to challenge and further the phenomenology and ecological psychology- inspired interaction design theory (Hummels & Lévy, 2013; Stienstra, 2015; Stienstra, 2016) and corresponding implications for design practice, the system was built for exploration and getting a grip on its sensitivities. The following situations that underline the characteristics of the proposed design paradigm occurred while interacting with the system in qualitative user confrontations:

The light intensifies when space is entered and dims when it is left again. Since the lights respond to the desired directedness, the lighting does not follow but goes ahead of the person. Turning, however, thus actuates several light bulbs over time and this makes the light move in front of the person. The Sensible Illumination thus enlightens the space of gaze which was experienced as "the light is part of me, it extends me". This suggests that the design enables immersion or engagement with the light. Nonetheless, it has to be noted that sensibility is required. That is, the continuity of light moving is appreciated. However, when light movement is mapped too direct, it is quite an evasive situation. Despite that the brightness and hue of lamps transition continuously over time, the 'switch' between covered enlighten areas is still discrete creating somewhat abrupt and disturbing transitions.

In case the gaze is already brightened by sunlight, the desire to intensify is not broadcasted and thus not picked up. When the desire increases, because of a sunset, the lamp continuously intensifies till the desire has been fulfilled. While the user becomes inactive, the spotlight fades out. Being active again re-activates the light in the space of gaze.

When two people meet in the same space, the light, as well as both people, starts to interplay. When both people turn to the same spot the spot illuminates. What is evident is that the people adjust their behavior in interaction to cope and control the light. It is a challenge to provide the light with a transforming behavior character as well to come forth to the dynamics of *contextuality* in people's behavior. The presupposed take on and use of people's desire to have light in front of them turned out to be useful. Nonetheless, the use of *desire* as a particular derivative of someone's *intentionality* requires caution, careful consideration and further validation in context.

Concluding remarks

The initial design explorations with the build system highlight a few characteristics of the theory and design practicality. The preliminary results from our qualitative user confrontations indicate that the idea to design for *in between about-content* upholds the potential to have meaning emerge mutually, i.e., emergent in interaction between person and system. The design exploration persuaded for engagement, yet at times, it occurred in an invasive manner. Paramount

to its functioning is *sensibility in continuity* that captures the person and light bulbs in a shared loop of engagement. The research will be furthered by gathering and systematically analyzing user impressions as well as behavior patterns that emerge. The phenomenology-informed ideas that meaning emerges in interaction and that engagement has a reciprocal character reveals that design could focus on emergent in-between meanings, rather than focusing the design on either the artefacts characteristics or user's experience. To design for an in-between meaning to emerge, it seems fruitful to focus on the continuous nature of perception and action to engage people and system with the *about-content* that lives in between.

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